

IMPROVING COMMUNICATION SKILLS OF THE INTERMEDIATE MULTI-GRADE LEARNER THROUGH ORAL LANGUAGE AND VOCABULARY READINESS (OLAVOR)

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Improving Communication Skills of the Intermediate Multi-grade Learner through Oral Language and Vocabulary Readiness (OLaVoR)

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Abstract

This action research aims to implement the school's reading intervention program designed by the researcher to enhance the reading proficiency levels of the intermediate multi-grade learners of Olag Pequeño Elementary School based on their reading profile for the school year 2022-2023. Furthermore, "Improving Communication Skills of Intermediate Multi-grade Learners in Olag Pequeno Elementary School through Oral Language and Vocabulary Readiness (OLaVoR)," aims to enhance literacy among students transitioning from remote learning to face-to-face classes post-pandemic. Implemented weekly, it targets MG Classes in the intermediate level to prepare students for academic success. Project TURO focuses on reading proficiency, utilizing diagnostic tools and modified instructional materials. "Hear it, Say it!" aids pronunciation and vocabulary through listening and speaking exercises during remedial classes. "Write it, Right?" emphasizes storytelling, vocabulary acquisition, and context clues exploration during weekly sessions. "#ICanSeeYou" promotes oral communication by describing images and objects using Filipino or English, fostering peer interaction and text analysis. Lastly, "InTONEation" hones proper tone and intonation through daily sentence recitation, aiming to improve communication skills for everyday use. These structured interventions address the specific needs of intermediate multi-grade learners, facilitating their academic growth and communication proficiency.

Keywords: *communication skills, intermediate multi-grade learner, oral language, vocabulary readiness*

Introduction

Many changes happened in this world during the pandemic, precisely the way of educating our children to protect and not be harmed and affected by this so-called COVID-19. Learning in the new normal is a big challenge for all teachers, students, and even parents because we do not know if our learners really learn the competencies they need to have to be prepared for their future. In the usual face-to-face classes, we see and know every capacity of each learner on how they perform during classes academically or not. Many strategies have been developed to conduct effective ways of educating our learners, such as online learning, blended, TV and radio-based, and the common modular learning. However, it cannot provide the holistic knowledge that the learners must possess to become more competitive in their academic performance.

In the new normal form of classes, we do not assess our learners if they perform well, especially in their oral language and vocabulary skills, if they can speak and read the words. It is upsetting that the school only depends on self-learning modular skills, and some of the students did not compile the activities; instead, the parents shall. While we are on our way to face-to-face classes, the learning transition is crucial.

According to Dubey et al. (2020), the pandemic has called for a pause in the ways and means of learning. The situation has prevented the learning actions for the students, which is why imbalances in learning are happening now. Therefore, educational institutions should think of the best and effective possible strategies, such as interventions that indeed benefit the learners while they are at home and at the same time in their transition to face-to-face class setting and that also pertain to protecting their mental health.

Since this pandemic affected our classes we also believe that there was no total quality education that may improve. However, if the school and the teachers insist on having a better quality education during this pandemic the school must create and develop different strategies in order to develop learners' oral language and literacy skills. Literacy acquisition occurs along a developmental continuum with origins in the preschool years. They need to learn the basic phonological skill that must be observed and monitored by the teachers to see if the children really keep up with the competencies in DepEd. Young children progress through a period of emergent literacy during which they develop the rudimentary skills, knowledge, and attitudes that prepare them for the acquisition of conventional literacy especially on their skill in communication and literacy-based form the study of Hariati (2021) that most students are now inclining with the ideas of online communication through different digitalize technology however in the Philippine setting of learning this developing communication skill might hard to improved since most of the students are favorable to be back at the school to continue and improve their skills.

Based from the current data result of the final grades under SMEA these multi-grade learners in OPES has below averages in English and Filipino subjects two of the major subject that develop language and literary skills. And in response to this problem the Learning Recovery Plan (LRP) of the Deped Camsur will be another source of motivation to pursue this project innovation towards helping and

improve the holistic efficacy of language and literacy skills of the intermediate learners under the multi-grade classes in the school (Madrid, 2022)

This study Improving Communication skills of the Intermediate Multi-grade Learners in Olag Pequeno Elementary School through Oral Language and Vocabulary Readiness (OLaVoR) will be conducted in order to evaluate and improve learners' oral language and literacy skills. OLaVoR stands to support the needed remediation to the young learners who have been victims of this education crisis brought by the COVID-19 pandemic. This is another plan to recover the effectiveness of the the intermediate grade levels for their language and literacy skills.

Research Questions

This action research aims to implement school's reading intervention program designed by the researcher to enhance the reading proficiency levels of the intermediate multi-grade learners of Olag Pequeño Elementary School based on their reading profile for the school year 2022-2023. Specifically, it will seek to answer the following questions:

1. What are the reading proficiency levels of the learners in oral reading based on the Phil-IRI assessment tool?
2. What is the level of effectiveness of intervention learning materials before and after using OLaVoR?
3. What is the significant effect of the communication skills of intermediate learners using Project OLaVoR?

Proposed Innovation, Intervention, and Strategy

Improving Communication skills of the Intermediate Multi-grade Learners in Olag Pequeno Elementary School through Oral Language and Vocabulary Readiness (OLaVoR) is an initiative to improve students' academic performance in literacy while all students are at the stage on the transitioning to face-to-face classes from the 2 years pandemic break. These interventions will be distributed every Friday in school whose offering MG Classes in intermediate. This is also in order to prepare them for the coming week and the result will also be done as to give another sets of instruments during Friday morning. The following are specific activities/project to be done in the district for the school year 2022-2023:

1. Project TURO: this Teaching and Understanding Reading Opportunity is an innovation project that will prepare effective materials for diagnostic and on the process of gathering data. This strategy focuses on the areas of reading such Phonemic Awareness, Phonics, Fluency, and vocabulary. Most of the intermediate level under multi-grade has the hard time to read independently because of some factors. This innovation will be participated by the teacher whose handling the intermediate classes with the modified IMs modified by the researcher as the tools for this intervention the students will participates this could be done in the integration of their topic and for remedial classes for every day 1 in the week.
2. Hear it, Say it!: this intervention will help learners listen to correct and accurate pronunciation of words and then they need to follow it. Through this they will also use the vocabulary words in their own sentences and shall write it in the modified activity sheet. This will be done during their remedial classes in the day 2 of the week. All students in multi-grade classes from grade 4 to grade 6 shall undergo this intervention program.
3. Write it, Right?: the learners will read a story to his/her peers with proper intonation and vocalization of words. They will write the heightened words from the story provided and shall find its correct context clues in the given situation. This will be done on every 3rd day of the week for their remedial classes.
4. #ICanSeeYou: the intermediate pupils will look at the picture or object then they will describe and give an opinion using Filipino or English they will rate accordingly with the rubrics. This is considered as text analysis wherein as they see the symbols/ objects they will have more communication with peers and oral language skill shall be enhanced. This is also be conducted under the class remedial subject
5. InTONEation: the learner in the intermediate level shall read the proper tone and intonation of the given sentences per day. As they enter the class they will read and recite the sentences they encounter and must be delivered. This is an intervention material will develop learners proper intonation, sounds in every sentences they use in their everyday living.

Methodology

Research Design

This action research will employ a descriptive method of research in discussing the answers to the research questions.

Participants

The participants of this study will be all intermediate students in Olag Pequeno Elementary school in Tinambac North District such as: 4 from Grade 4, 7 from Grade 5, and 4 from Grade 6 for the coming school year 2022-2023.

Procedure

The following are the methods to answer the question stated in this action research.

For question number 1: What is the reading proficiency levels of the learners in oral reading based on the Phil- IRI assessment tool?

To identify the level of the academic performances of these students the Grade 4 learners will be identify based from the results in their CRLA during their 3rd grade level. For the Grade 5 and 6 the Phil-Iri will be the instrument by conducting pre-test to identify the pupils with reading deficiency and the independent readers. With the guidance of class adviser the rubrics and the test questions for pre-test will be given in order to see to it that the implementation of the pre-test is accurate. And to test their oral communication the sets of test will be administer and the rubrics shall be discussed beforehand.

For question number 2: What is the level of effectiveness of intervention learning materials before and after using project OLaVoR?

The data will be collected based on the total number of participants who will undergo these interventions. That date will be presented using tabular form to show effectiveness of the interventions such as: a) Project TURO; b) Hear it, Say it!; c) Write it, Right?; d) #ICanSeeYou; and inTONEation.

For question number 3: What is the significant effect of the intermediate students under Multi-grade classes using the Project OLaVoR?

That data will be collected based on the significant improvement on the effectiveness level of the interventions. Posttest will be conducted to see how the usefulness of the interventions used in this research differ. Tabular form will be utilized to present the data on this research objective to show the difference between the level of competency on the pre-implementation and the level of competency on post-implementation.

Data Analysis Plan

For question number 1: What is the reading proficiency levels of the learners in oral reading based on the Phil- IRI assessment tool?

The score will be collected from the test that the students done to get the mean and the performance level of the students from grades 4 to 6 whose under the multi-grade classes. The respondents will undergo pre-test written and oral to see the sanding of the learners who will be most be benefited of this innovation. All participated respondents shall be interpreted as very low, low, moderate, high, and very high. This rate will be based on the modified rubrics of the researcher through written and oral.

For question number 2: What is the level of effectiveness of intervention learning materials before and after using OLaVoR?

To determine the levels of acceptance of the intervention/strategies/methods used in the material, the respondents will survey using the Likert Scale with 5 indicators revealing their attitudes towards intervention such as Project TURO, Hear it, Say it!, Write it, right?, #ICanSeeYou, and the inTONEation. The respondents will rate each intervention program with Ineffective when the students doesn't fell that the intervention is good, less effective when the respondents feel that the intervention has something to tel in good for literacy improvement. Also, Fair when the respondents find the intervention as in fifty percent good and might effective, and Effective if almost they like the intervention and Very Effective when the learners find the intervention better to use in the remedial instruction o hat must be continue to help more learners.

For question number 3: What is the significant effect of the intermediate students under multi-grade classes using the Project OLaVoR?

This will be analyze by the Mean final rating of the pretest conducted and the post-test the two test will be compare and calculated to see the weighed mean in order to see that the interventions are very effective in developing learners whose struggling communication.

Action Research Work Plan and Timelines

<i>Activities</i>	<i>Time Frame</i>	<i>Person/S Involved</i>	<i>Means Of Verification</i>
PRE-IMPLEMENTATION PLAN			
Step 1: DIAGNOSING – Identifying or defining a problem	July 4, 2022 (1 day)	Teacher Parents Pupils	Accomplished Pre-test
Step 2: ACTION PLANNING – Considering alternative courses of action			
Consult with the school head/PSDS regarding the intention / plan to conduct the research	July 4, 2022 (1 day)	School Head, PSDS Teacher	Minutes of consultation & planning meeting
Submit action research proposal for approval	July 14, 2022 (1 day)	Researcher	Approved action research proposal
Inform both the teachers and the administration of the study to be conducted—its nature and target output; solicit the group's commitment to support	July 15, 2022 (1 day)	Teacher Parent	Minutes of meeting with the school head and teachers

the conduct of the research.

IMPLEMENTATION PLAN

Step 3: TAKING ACTION – Selecting a course of action

Implementation of the innovation Project NONG

1. Project TURO
2. Hear it, Say it!
3. Write it, Right?
4. #ICanSeeYou
5. inTONEation

August to September 2022

Teacher-Researcher /School Head Pupils

Implemented interventions

Step 4: EVALUATING – Studying the consequences of an action

Conduct of the first stage of data gathering among student-respondents

First week of September 2022

Teacher-Researcher Pupils

Accomplished research tools

Use of research tools in analyzing the data gained from the research

2nd week of September 2022

Teacher-Researcher Parents

Analyzed data from accomplished tools

Step 5: SPECIFYING LEARNING – Identifying general findings

Analysis of generated data

3rd Week of September 2022

Teacher-Researcher Parents

Research data and outcome analyzed

POST-IMPLEMENTATION PLAN

Prepare and submit action research write-up

1st week of November 2022

Researcher

Accepted Action research write-up

Convey results of the study to the stakeholders for possible benchmarking

As schedule

Researcher and other stakeholders

Minutes of meeting

Research dissemination – presentation to research forum

As schedule

Certificate as presenter, TO, Communication

Utilization / improvement of the studied innovation in the succeeding school year

Researcher and other teachers

Utilized/improved the strategy/ program used

Plans for Dessimination And Utilization

Research Dissemination Plan. Results of this action research will be shared with the school head and to the entire school as well as the other competent teachers in Olag Pequeño Elementary School, Tinambac North District. The researcher likewise wants to express her willingness to guide other teachers in implementing the said research for professional growth and development.

Data Utilization Plan. Data from this initiative will be used in crafting project proposals, which will form part of the 2022 and 2023 Annual Implementation Plan, School Improvement Plan, and school policy formulation.

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